

‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ - An Unique Megalithic Rock Art Depiction special reference to Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh.

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ABSTRACT

The Rock art occur in various geologically formations, sand stone, limestone, granite, shale, etc.¹ Paintings belonging to Megalithic period are noticed both on natural rock surface and on the monuments constructed out of rock material. Further, the modern rock art research rejects the reliance on stylistic reasoning, i.e. the idea that researchers can reliably identify styles, or that stylistic similarity inevitably proves cultural unity. Many of these ideas have been questioned and even rejected, so it would be inappropriate to continue using the guidelines and philosophies developed by these approaches. The rock art in south India also revealed striking regional features in terms of thematic comparison, styles and chronological context in different ecological niches. The rock art corpus of South India is the second largest one outside the Vindhyan formations. Among the symbols depicted, the most interesting shows a circle with a trident. This symbol appears to be the hall mark of Megalithic petroglyph art, although it is not totally absent in the painted forms. The symbol “Circle with Trident” stands out as an unique symbol apart from other geometrical symbols. It has been densely found in many of Megalithic burial sites of Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh when compared with the rest of Indian Megaliths. The placement of the trident strokes depicted in varying positions on the circle, the number may vary in various sites. The trident strokes in some sites are straight is some they are curved.

Key Words: Symbol, Rock art, petroglyph art, Vindhyan, Cultural dynamics, Neolithic habitation

Introduction

The Term 'Rock Art' is generally used to define several types of artistic examples in the form of Paintings, Bruisings, Engravings, Peckings, etc. on bare rock surfaces of caves, Rock shelters and isolated rock boulders. These forms of Rock art occur in Various geologically formations, sand stone, limestone, granite, shale, etc.¹ Paintings belonging to Megalithic period are noticed both on natural rock surface and on the monuments constructed out of rock material. It is interestin to note that, so far Rayalaseema region has yielded the largest number of sites with paintings on megalithic monuments and in Rock shelters.²

Moreover, modern rock art research rejects the reliance on stylistic reasoning, i.e. the idea that researchers can reliably identify styles, or that stylistic similarity inevitably proves cultural unity. It must be appreciated that many of these models and practices are the legacy of a period when rock art studies were entirely tied to archaeology, and when such studies were conducted with essentially Eurocentric ideas of past societies and their cultural dynamics. Many of these ideas have been questioned and even rejected, so it would be inappropriate to continue using the guidelines and philosophies developed by these approaches. Modern rock art studies emphasize the importance of epistemologically sound reasoning, of scientific methods of enquiry, and of the practical application of refutations' or post-processualist thinking.³

Rock art in India, on the base where we stand now, is beyond any application of scientific or technological base in real sense, in spite of the research being initiated in 1860's. Though initial studies were hampered by Euro-centric Pre conception of the English archaeologists, it is only after 1960's investigations were intensified to develop a possible link between rock art and archaeological data to ascertain its antiquity in terms of their historical relevance. The way we see things are after influenced by what we know and what we believe. Therefore, it is time for the researcher, intended in Indian rock art, to look for its meaningful interpretation keeping in view the profile and continuity of Indian rock art in the Indian perspective supported by archaeological, literary, ethnographic and even oral tradition.⁴

The earliest discovery of petroglyphs (bruising) as the Kupgallu hill of Bellary district was made by Fawcett (1892) who with the assistance of Herbert T. Knox and Robert Sewell discovered them in 1891. Bruce Foote later visited the site and discovered some more bruising and engravings in 1903.⁵ Fawcett also discovered rock carvings in the Edakal cave in the Khozikode district of Kerala.⁶ Munn was the first to record the rock paintings in south India. He noticed 3 rock paintings in the Hire Benakal hill range of granitic gneiss and gave a brief description of those paintings.⁷ Tamil nadu still remains the status of "Terra

incognito” in the field of rock art research. Rajan⁸ informs that there are 25 known rock art sites in Tamil Nadu. Neumayer Erwin further informs that he has explored more than 30 rock art sites in Tamil nadu.⁹

In the Southern Deccan, the rock paintings of the hunters and gatherers were mainly found situated in the quartzite regions. The more outstanding ones are found in the surroundings of Badami, in the Bijapur district of Karnataka, Ketavaram in the Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh and Chintakunta in the Kadapa district of the same state.¹⁰ The rock art tradition in Andhra Pradesh appears as early as Mesolithic phase. All the subsequent phases of the Prehistoric and Proto-historic periods, Early Historic and Medieval periods are also represented.

The rock art in south India also revealed striking regional features in terms of thematic comparison, styles and chronological context in different ecological niches. The role of rock art in “information transmission” and the ethno-archaeological concept of ‘dry season aggregation and wet-season dispersal’ should be analyzed.¹¹

Rock art in South India was recognized by antiquarians as early as 1892. The rock art corpus of South India is the second largest one outside the Vindhyan formations. A host of scholars, have contributed to the discovery, documentation and analysis of the Rock art data in this part of the sub-continent Allchin, Bhat, Chandramouli & Narasimham, Fawcett, Gordon, Gordon & Allchin, Krishna Moorty, Krishna Sastry, Mahadevan, Mathpal, Munn, Neumayer, Paddayya, Rajan, Ramabrahmam, Rami Reddy, Sarma,A.V.N, Subramanyam, Sundara, Venkatasubbaiah, Sivakumar Challa and Narayana Jangari¹²

The Rock Art themes comprising of animals such as deer species, rabbit, tortoise, mangoose, porcupine, birds, human and anthropomorphic figures and geometric figures done in red color can be date to Mesolilthic Period. The Megalithic art contain in majority geometric symbols, human figures, anthropomorphic figures, animal figures, such as horse, etc. Among the geometric symbols, which comprise the majority of the Megalithic rock art, both in paintings and petroglyphs.¹³

The Circle with a trident Symbol:

Among the symbols depicted, the most interesting shows a circle with a trident. This symbol appears to be the hall mark of Megalithic petroglyph Art, although it is not totally absent in the painted forms. At Mudumula, Chagatur, Naidupalli and Budigapalli, this symbol is found either on Megalithic burials or in the rock shelters close to them. At Naidupalli, it occurs in a variety of shapes and sizes. That the symbol has

religious/Cultic significance is implied in one composition in which several human figures are shown dancing in front of this circle with a trident symbol. In another depiction, this symbol is transformed in such a way as to look like an anthropomorph.¹⁴

In the group noticed at Regonda two little men ride a disproportionately big horse. There are also tridents bisecting a circle below and simple tridents without circles. Several such tridents bisecting circles below were indented on the orthostats of some Megalithic cist burials at Chagatur. Further, at Mudumala, a village in the Mukthal taluk of Mahaboobnagar district, where the existence of alignments was reported, and the rock brusings contained many identical figures of tridents on circles besides linear representations of a Mother Goddess and a bull. These are called Nandipada symbol on the obverse and the looped designs are found very commonly in the Megalithic rock painting and rock brusings.¹⁵

We are still in a lurch regarding the religious beliefs and objects of worship of the Megalithic period. Guru Raja Rao¹⁶ most ingeniously suggested that the occurrence of trident or trisula and the sulam, the spike – kike object in the Megaliths have acquired a religious significance among the later Dravidian – speaking Hindus of South India. The trident is invariably associated with Siva and other deities like Durga, etc.

Recent findings of ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ in Rayalaseema :

1. Aspari :-

Aspari¹⁷ is a mandal headquarter which is situated on the way from Kurnool – Ballari main road in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. Towards north east of present village with distance of 1 km. situated a hillock with dyke formation locally known as “Nallakonda” (Black hill). At foothills of the dyke formation there is taken place a Neolithic habitation with Neolithic hand axes, Celts, and different types of pottery, and on the hillock there is taken place rock art with different human and animal figures and ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ are located in the form of engravings.

2. Bodabanda :-

Bodabanda¹⁸ village located on the way from Yemmiganuru – Adoni main road 10 km. southwest from Yemmiganuru mandal in Kurnool District, towards east of the present village dyke formation is noticed, near the foot of the dyke boulders nearly 10 – 15 megalithic stone circles are noticed. few engravings are depicted on the stone circles boulders in the form of animals, human riding on the animals, bulls, humped bulls, gathering of humans with raising hands, probably they are in prayer, few ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ are also identified, some of the boulders having the engravings of humans with raised swords on the left hand side, and on the right hand side with protective shields, reveals rivalry. Few ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings are also identified on the boulders. Basically the site reveals Megalithic in affiliation, but animal’s depictions are engraved, significant to Neolithic period. Chronologically the continuation of cultures form to Neolithic to megalithic noticed

3. Bommakuyana :-

Bommakuyana¹⁹ is a dyke out crop hillock which is situated 1 km. southwest from Erukalacheruvu village situated 34 km. east from Devanakonda mandal head quarters in Kurnool district. On the slope of ‘Bommakuyana’, ‘hill of Rock engravings’, there are ten megalithic stone circles with measuring 4-6 meters in diameter are situated. In this site Bommakuyana the stone circles are located near the foot of the hillock, in the nearby vicinity on the top of the hillock dyke formation was noticed on the boulders majority of the depictions are ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’, Humans with a long tail. In this site humans with long tail are peculiar noticed in this devanakonda mandal. These types of tailed figures with white ochre were noticed in the Bhogeswaram Rock art shelter which is located at the distance of about 150 km. in the Gadivemula mandal of Kurnool district. The only peculiar feature noticed in this site Bommakuyana, this tailed humans are engraved on dyke stones, at Bhogeswaram site the same stylistic depictures are painted in

white ochre, this shows that aesthetic sense of prehistoric man was continued in engraving are painted in the stone of Kurnool district.

4. Chintakunta :-

Chintakunta²⁰ is a village which is situated 3 km. south east from Kosigi mandal head quarters in Kurnool District. Towards North West of present village with distance of 1 km. There is a granite hillock locally known as “Polimeravva Gutta”, behind this hillock, in between two hillocks there is dyke out crop pebbles are situated, in that place there is a Megalithic and Rock Art site is located with stone circles and engravings, here nearly 10 – 15 stone circles are located with measuring 6 – 8 meters in diameter.

The Chintakunta stone circle site has peculiar features in the stone circle burial pattern. Normally in other parts of the Kurnool district the dyke formations noticed in a crowded, and vertical in form, but in this Chintakunta stone circle burial site the dyke boulders are scattered in a length of 500 X 100 meters in measurements, normally this place and hillock was locally called as “Polimeravva Gutta”, in the scattered dyke formations stone boulders are arranged in circular manner, on these dyke stone boulders rock engravings are noticed. Particularly in this site animal figure are absent, a few human figures are noticed in eroding manner, and the remaining engravings have significant features of ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’.

5. Devanakonda :-

Devanakonda²¹ is a mandal headquarter, which is situated on the way from Kurnool – Ballari main road in Kurnool district. Towards east adjoining of the Devanakonda there is a dyke hillock locally known as “Brahmaiah Gudi Konda” is situated, in the hillock on some dyke boulders few engravings are identified with animals and majority are ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings and totally this site affiliated to Megalithic rock art and few evidences of Neolithic affiliation.

6. Eddupenta :-

Eddupenta²² is a village which is situated 17 km. south west from Dhone mandal headquarters in Kurnool district. Towards east of present village with distance of 2 km. in agricultural fields there is small bare rock locally known as “Sappamma Chenu”(Place of Local village goddess Sappamma) is situated, on that bare rock there are ten stone circles with measuring 4 m. in diameter are situated. Surrounding of these stone circles some of the boulders poses engravings affiliated to different styles of humped bulls and some more ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ were also encountered. Due to the majority of these humped bulls villagers literally named this village as “Eddupenta”.

7. Erukala Cheruvu :-

Erukala Cheruvu²³ is a village which is saturate 34 km. east from Devanakonda manda headquarters in Kurnool district. Towards north west of present village with distance of 3 km. in between agricultural fields there is dyke formation is situated which is locally known as “Nallakonda”(Black hill). At the foot and slopes of the dyke formation there is a megalithic site is situated with ten stone circles with measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameter, and on the top of the hillock there are some engravings of rock art with four legged animal figures, animal riders, are identified, in addition to that ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings were also noticed.

8. Garugupatti :-

Garugupatti²⁴ is located 2 km. east from Nunusuralla village at a distance of 20 km. north east from Tuggali mandal in Kurnool District. Previous this Garugupatti area a flow of seasonal stream locally named as “Peddavagu” noticed. Nearly 30 – 40 megalithic burials of stone circles with cairn packing measuring 8 – 10 m. in diameter, among one of the stone circles boulder four ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings were noticed.

9. Gavigatlu :-

Gavigatlu²⁵ is a village located 20 km. northwest from Pedda kaduburu mandal in Kurnool District, towards southwest of the present village at a distance of 2 km. in between agricultural fields, there is a bare land is situated with granite outcrops. In this place there is a megalithic site is situated with me ten stone circles with measuring 6-8 meters in diameter, on the stone boulders rock art engravings are noticed, ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ and two large Tridents in squarely pattern, some rough traces of humped bulls are identified, but depictions are not authentic to their size and posture.

10. Goduguratigutta:-

Goduguratigutta²⁶ is a small bare rock land which is situated 15 km. south west from Yammiganuru mandal headquarters and 4 km. south from Kotekkal village panchayat in Kurnool district. In this bare rock land there is a megalithic site with five stone circles with measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameter, these stone circles were made with outcrop pebbles and granite boulders. Among these stone circle monuments few boulders engraved with ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ in addition to that some more engravings are noticed, but the scholar was unable to identified these engravings because of weathering. In adjoining of this site there is a rock is naturally situated on another rock like an umbrella, hence this place is called by local people as “Goduguratigutta” (Heap of umbrella shaped Hillock).

11. H.Muravani :-

H.Muravani²⁷ is a village which is situated 3 km. south from Yemmiganuru – Kosigi main road in Peddakaduburu mandal in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. Towards south of present village a dyke hillock is situated which is locally known as “Basavannagutta” (Hillock of Basavanna (Bull)). At the foothills of the hillock there five stone circles are situated with measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameters, on the top of the hillock and vicinity of the stone circles some engravings are identified, majority are humans with raised tail, some are holding weapons, few ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings were also identified.

12. Idupulapaya :-

Idupulapaya²⁸ rock shelter was found close to Idupulapaya IIIT and YSR Ghat. A water stream trail leads to the site. The main rock shelter is situated on a plateau, and it faces a local creek. At 10.5 meters above ground level, there is a cave with a narrow platform. The drawing is found around the ground-level rock cave structures and on the ceiling wall of the upper deck cave structure. The upper plate is reached through a hard vertical rock climb. The route to the top plate is highlighted by several creative drawings. All the pictures on the site found by the team are painted in white ochre material using brush technique.

Most of the paintings are in the open. The team speculates that there may be megalithic tombs in and around the rock bunker, which is covered by thick vegetation. The team studied various themes of the white paint drawings scattered throughout the shelter. The various pictures drawn can be classified as Stick drawings of humans as individual warriors with swords, human warriors riding on horseback holding swords, humans in groups in war scenes and performing rituals, mask-decorated man, birdman or a man sacrificing a bull, drawings of elephant, horse, tiger, humped bull, religious symbols like Swastika, trident, a circle with three spikes, symbols like a ladder, circles, and ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ can be found on the rocks on the bank of the stream.

13. J.M.Tanda :-

Jeevaralla Mala Tanda²⁹ village is located 5 km. northeast of Pattikonda mandal in Kurnool District, towards southeast of present village at a distance of 2 km. there is some dyke out crop pebbles are arranged as megalithic stone circles. There are nearly ten On and around stone circle noticed rock art engravings with humped bulls, and ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’, further some of the engravings are not clearly identified.

14. Kamavaram :-

Kamavaram is a village which is situated 6 km. east from Kawthalam mandal headquarters in Kurnool district. Towards north east of present village with a distance of 2 km. in between agricultural lands there is a granite hillock situated which is locally known as “Manisigottu Timmappa Konda”, towards northeast adjoin of this hillock at foot hills there is some dyke outcrop pebbles are located in that place there is a megalithic site is situated with ten stone circles with measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameter, on stone circle boulders and surrounding boulders there is rock art encountered with engravings. Majority of the engravings are animals, animal raiders, standing humans, one of the engraving depicts a square pattern probably it may be a rural game, ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings are commonly noticed in this site.

Here in this hillock there is a local myth have been followed by people. On this hillock there are two boulders which are naturally forming which looking like two human are standing. According to the local tales, once upon a time two people of brother and sister went to forest for collect firewood, on that time brother behave abuse with sister and spoil sister’s virginity, then she get angry and cursed to the brother and then the brother become as standing stone then even sister also become standing stone. The local people called these standing stones as “Niluvurallu”.

15. Kappatralla :-

Kappatralla³⁰ village which is located 2 km. south from Kurnool – Bellary main road, and 15 km. northeast from Devanakonda mandal in Kurnool District, towards southeast of present village at a distance of 1 km. noticed hillock with dyke boulders. On that hillock slopes noticed ten megalithic stone circles measuring 6 – 8 meters in diameter, on and around the stone circle boulders noticed engravings with animals, animal raiders, war scenes of animal raider holding weapon on his right hand and fighting with a

man standing on the field with weapon on his right hand, few ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ engravings also identified.

16. Katarikonda :-

Katari Konda³¹ is a village which is situated 22 km. southwest from Krishnagiri mandal headquarters in Kurnool district. Towards south east of present village with distance of 1 km. there is a granite hillock locally known as “Teegala Rai Konda”. On the foot hills and slopes of the hillock there is dyke out crops were situated. These out crops were arranged as megalithic stone circles with measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameter, there are nearly ten stone circles are located, on stone circle boulders and around the boulders contains a few engravings with depict humans and four legged animals, particularly goat engravings is identified, among remaining four legged animals few animals having horns, two humans identified with sword noticed in the waist region, the remaining engravings are identified with ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’, all the engravings are noticed in the eroding condition.

17. Lakkasagaram :-

Lakkasagaram³² village is located 22 km. southwest from Krishnagri mandal in Kurnool District, towards northeast of present village at a distance of 1 km. noticed dyke formations in the form of boulders, in the vicinity of the boulders noticed a megalithic site with 10 – 15 stone circles measuring 4 – 6 meters in diameter. On the sides and top of the megalithic stone circle boulders noticed rock art engravings, majorly depict ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ in different descriptive forms. A peculiar ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ identified with a wavy tail to downwards, another ‘The Circle with a trident Symbol’ could not identify properly, and this type of peculiar engravings was noticed in this Lakkasagaram site only. A beautifully engraved fish was noticed consist of head, tail and fins, even the eye of the fish was also engraved, and this type of fish is peculiar for this site. This shows that the Megalithic people normally stay to the nearby water localities like streams, and tanks. This shows that fish is taken as food for their livelihood strategies.

Conclusion

The symbol “Circle with Trident” stands out as a unique symbol apart from other geometrical symbols. It has been densely found in many of Megalithic burial sites of Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh when compared with the rest of Indian Megaliths. The placement of the trident strokes depicted in varying positions on the circle, the number may vary (two, three, four or six) in various sites. The trident strokes in some sites are straight is some they are curved. On studying the patterns at Naidupalli and idupulapaya one may conclude the symbol is associated with an ritual of funeral or healing process during the Megalithic culture.

It is noticed that some existing religious cults has adopted complete symbol or part of the symbol in contemporary period. Lord Shiva and Goddesses shakthi of Hindu religion are depicted carrying a Trident. Almost a similar circle with trident symbol is seen in Hyderabad region by local community during the religious procession and also worshiped in the name of 'Bibi-Ka-Alam or Bibi-Ka-Alawa is an annual procession during Muharram. Further study is required to establish the sequence of adoption of the circle with trident symbols later period of time by the various religious cults.

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